

Translaminar Fracture Analysis in **Hybrid** Fibre-Reinforced Composites through 4D in-situ Synchrotron Tomography

Sina AhmadvashAghbash, G. Broggi, A. Aydemir, A. Argyropoulos, J. Cugnoni,
V. Michaud, M. Mehdikhani and Y. Swolfs

Translaminar Fracture: Why Do We Care?

Goal & Objectives

Goal:

To better understand translaminar fracture crack propagation at the microscale.

Objectives:

- To design a new mini compact tension specimen that:
 - Is geometrically suitable for 4D synchrotron radiation computed tomography,
 - Can yield stable crack propagation.

3D View: Swiss Light Source SLS

Compact Tension Experiments: Specimen Design

Compact Tension Experiments: F- δ Results

Voxel size **800 nm**
GigaFRoST camera as the detector
polychromatic beam (energy = 24 keV)

3D & 2D Slices

Scans reconstruction using SLS in-house absorption-based algorithm (Gridrec)

F. Marone et al. 2012

Complex Fracture Morphology

Detailed pull-out characterisation
 90° cracks ahead of 0° cracks

3D & 2D Slices

200 μm
↔

3D & 2D Slices

250 μm

3D & 2D Slices: Various Load Levels

Force [N]

Fibre Breaks Ahead of the Crack Tip

Ply-by-Ply Hybrid

Ply-by-Ply Hybrid

First 90° Ply Block

Second 90° Ply Block

Third 90° Ply Block

Ply-by-Ply Hybrid

First 0° Ply Block

Second 0° Ply Block

Ply-by-Ply Hybrid

Fibre-by-Fibre Hybrid

Fibre-by-Fibre Hybrid

Significant bundle pull-out

Also noted in a high-strain baseline specimen

Fibre-by-Fibre Hybrid

The difference between the crack fronts at 0° and 90° is $595 \pm 96 \mu m$

Fibre-by-Fibre Hybrid

R-Curves: Fracture Toughness Values

low-strain baseline

fibre-by-fibre hybrid

FE Model: Defining Fracture Behaviour

FE Model: Defining Fracture Behaviour

Conclusions

Results:

- The mini-protruded design, with a pre-crack half its length, results in stable crack propagation,
- 2D slices reveal advancing crack fronts in the 90° plies and lagging fronts in the 0° plies on fracture surface,
- FEM can capture this!
- Interlayer & intrayarn hybrids have a higher translaminal fracture toughness than either of their two baseline configurations.

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sina.ahmadvashaghash@kuleuven.be

[@hyfisyn](https://www.instagram.com/hyfisyn)

EPFL

HyFiSyn

Composite materials group

KU LEUVEN

MATERIAALKUNDE